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An Integrated Approach to Diagnose and Treatment of Palmoplantar Psoriasis - A case study

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Abstract

Psoriasis is a chronic disease in which the immune system becomes overactive causing skin cells to multiply too quickly. It is skin disease that causes a rash with itchy, scaly patches, most commonly on the knees, elbows, trunk and scalp. In Allopathy and *Ayurveda* many drugs and herbs have proven efficacy in psoriasis but integrated treatment is more effective than any other. We report about integrated treatment in 30 years old female patient with Palmoplantar psoriasis presented with itching, pain and fissuring symptoms on palm and feet. The treatment protocol was adopted as per modern pathophysiology and *Ayurvedic samprapti* and patient cured completely within 3 months of the treatment and have not reported any recurrence even after 2 years of follow up

Keywords : Palmoplantar Psoriasis, *Panchtiktaghrith guggulu*, *Gandhaka rasayana*, *Mahatiktaka ghrita*

Introduction:

Psoriasis is a chronic disease in which the immune system becomes overactive causing skin cells to multiply too quickly. Patches of skin become scaly and inflamed most often on the scalp, elbow, knees but other parts of the body can be affected as well. Scientist do not fully understand what causes psoriasis but they know that it involves a mix of genetics and environmental factors[1]. Types of psoriasis: [1]

1. Plaque psoriasis -this is the most common kind and it appears as raised, red patches of skin that are covered by silvery white scales the patches usually develop in a symmetrical pattern on the body and tend to appear on the scalp, trunk, limbs, especially the elbows and knees.
2. Guttate psoriasis- This type usually appears in

children or young adults and look like small, red dots, typically on the torso or limbs outbreaks are often triggered by an upper respiratory tract infection such as strep throat.

3. Pustular psoriasis- In this type pus filled bumps called pustules surrounded by red skin appear it usually affects the hands and feet but there is form that covers most of the body.
4. Inverse psoriasis - This form appears as smooth red patches in folds of skin such as beneath the breasts or in the groin or armpits rubbing and sweating can make it worse.
5. Erythrodermic psoriasis - This is a rare but severe form of psoriasis characterized by red, scaly skin over most of the body it can be triggered by a bad sunburn or taking certain medications such as corticosteroids erythrodermic psoriasis often develops in

- people who have a different type of psoriasis that is not well controlled and it can be very serious.
- Nails psoriasis - Nail psoriasis is even more common in people who have psoriatic arthritis. having symptoms pitting of nails, tender painful nails separation of nail from bed.
 - Psoriatic arthritis - psoriatic arthritis is a condition where you have both psoriatic and arthritic. In more than 80% of cases, people had psoriasis for an average of 12 yrs before getting psoriatic arthritis. About 90% of people with it also have nail changes[2].

Diagnosis: skin biopsy

Most of the time psoriasis can be diagnosed just by examining the skin. But for the confirmed diagnosis and to rule out other causes of symptoms such as eczema or cutaneous lupus a skin biopsy may be performed.

Aim: To encourage integrated approach in Psoriasis for its early management.

Case Study:

Patient Information: A 30-year-old female homemaker had been diagnosed as Palmoplantar psoriasis and was treated by a dermatologist from where the patient was taking allopathic treatment (Methotrexate -once in week or 2-4 times in week, Etanercept - injected twice a week upto 12 weeks , Emollient)from 3 years with regular follow-ups. Topical and systemic immunosuppressive therapy was resulted in symptomatic relief from this treatment. Personal history revealed that the patient's general health was good. All the blood tests (routine tests) were within a normal range. No concomitant illness was found associated. However, due to a recurring pattern caused by the unknown aggravating factors, the patient discontinued allopathic treatment and consulted to our clinic.

Clinical findings

The patient presented with erythematous plaques on the palm and feet (sole). The affected skin was found with a deep painful fissures. The patient was suffering from intense itching and burning sensation

on palm and feet. At the time of the case presentation, no signs of psoriatic arthritis and nail bed psoriasis were found.

Fig 1 - Photographs of affected areas before and after one month of treatment

General examination

Body temperature (97.6 °F), Pulse (88/min), and Blood Pressure (118/86) were within normal limit.

Systemic examination

In systemic examination, respiratory and cardiovascular system found normal. The patient was restless due to itching and burning sensation over psoriatic lesions.

Asthavidha pariksha ;

Nadi (pulse) – Pittakaphaja;

Mala (stool)– Sandra-picchila, bowel habit was regular;

Mutra (urine) – Prakrita;

Jivha (tongue)– Shveta-picchila, Sama (coated);

Shabda – Prakrita;

Sparsha (touch)– Ushna;

Drika (vision) – Prakrita;

Aakriti – Madhyam (medium built).

Nidana panchaka :

Nidana – Viruddhahara sevana (simultaneous use of milk and salty snacks) and Raktadushtikar Ahara-vihara (excessive use of salty food, sour food like pickles, curd and sitting a long time in direct sunlight);

Samprapti –

Dosha – Pitta, Kapha and Rakta;

Dushya – Rasadhatu, Raktadhatu and Mamsadhatu;

Agni – Mandagni; Aam – Jatharagni and Dhatvagni janya;

Strotasa – Rasavaha, Raktavaha and Mamsavaha;

Adhithana – Twaka;

Rogamarga – Bahya;

Vyadhi Swabhava – Chirakari (chronic);

Sadhyasadhyata -Kricchrasadhya (difficult to treat);

Poorva roopa – Abhyantara daha (feeling of warmth), **Kandu** (itching), **Mukhapaka** (mouth ulcers) sometimes and **Mandagni** (anorexia);

Roopa: Jwara (fever), **Trishna** (thrust), **Daha** (burning sensation), **Kandu**, **Tvakavaivarnyata** (in present case, the affected skin was found with a deep painful fissures on palm and feet.), **Balahani** (generalised weakness);

Upashaya :Bahyashita; sparsha and Abhyanga (improvement on wet cold sponging and oil application)

Anupashaya – Ushna sparsha (increased symptoms on work in hot and humid climate).

Diagnostic assessment :All routine blood tests were within a normal range (**CBC, LFT, KFT, Blood glucose test ,Lipid profile etc is within a normal range**). The patient was not ready for tissue biopsy due to unaffordable cost. Therefore, based on clinical presentation, distribution of the skin damage, the case diagnosis was confirmed as palmoplantar psoriasis.

Therapeutic Interaction :

All previous oral and topical (Allopathic) medications were stopped. In this case, an integrated approach has been taken into consideration. According to *Ayurveda samprapti*, the involvement of *pitta* and *kapha dosha* ascertained by observing the clinical presentation such as *Daha* (burning sensation), *Kandu* (itching), *Raktavarnata* (redness), and the nature of skin lesions. Vitiating *pitta* and *kapha dosha* found involved in the pathological progress. The details of the internal and external medications prescribed have been mentioned in table no. 1

Table 1 - List of internal and external medications with dose, adjuvant, and duration.

Sr. No.	Formulation	Dose, frequency and time	Adjuvant	Duration
1	Injection Kenacort (Triamcinolone Acetonide) 40mg IM -Abbott pharma	Weekly once upto 1 month and then in after 15 days upto 2 months	—	3 Month
2	Panchtiktaghrith guggulu (Tablet)	1 gm (2 tablets) twice daily, after meal	Lukewarm water	3 Month
3	Gandhaka rasayana (Tablet)	250 mg (2 tablets) twice daily, after breakfast	Lukewarm water	3 Month
4	Mahatiktaka ghrita	2 gm (4 capsules), once daily on an empty stomach at early morning	Warm water	3 Month
5	Mahamanjishthadi Kwath	20 mL of kwath, twice daily after meal	50 mL of normal water	3 Month
6	Urtiplex Lotion with Gammascab Lotion (charaka pharma)	Topical application at night	—	3 Month
7	Immupsora oil (charaka pharma)	Twice a day, Topical application	—	3 Month
8	Dr Reckeweg R65 Psoriasis Drops	15 drops twice a days before food	1/2 cup of water	Next 9 months
9	Strict dietary plan	Restricted use of salt, sour food items, curd, old butter, milk and sweet products, meat and fish, overeating etc. Fast-food and soft or Hard drinks strictly be avoided	—	2 Years

Timeline

In the present case, all the treatment was continued for 3 months and follow up has been taken for one year. *Pathyahara* (A strict dietary plan) continued for two years after along with the active treatment to check the recurrence of psoriasis.

Follow up and outcomes

The Follow-ups details with timeline, treatment protocol, and periodic clinical outcome have been mentioned in Table 2. The psoriatic lesions with all its signs and symptoms cured. No adverse events

witnessed during the treatment. Photographs of affected areas before and after the one month of treatment is shown in Figure 1. The patient kept only on a strict dietary regimen for two years but no recurrence observed.

Table 2 - Follow-up history and clinical outcomes.

Timeline	Dates	Treatment plan	Periodic clinical outcomes
Onset of treatment	02/05/2021	As per Table 1	Integrated treatment started.
Follow-up 1	09/05/2021	As per Table 1	Subjective improvement in signs and symptoms. Itching reduced.
Follow-up 2	16/05/2021	As per Table 1	Subjective changes in signs and symptoms. Itching and burning reduced.
Follow-up 3	23/05/2021	As per Table 1	Significant improvement in symptoms i.e., very minimal itching and burning sensation left now
Follow-up 4	06/06/2021	As per Table 1	No itching and burning sensation.
Follow-up 5	20/06/2021	As per Table 1	Fissures on hand cured completely
Follow-up 6	04/07/2021	As per Table 1	Fissures on feet cured completely.
Follow-up 7	18/07/2021	As per Table 1	Recovered completely. No relapse in any sign and symptom.
Follow-up 8	10/04/2022	Homeopathic treatment along with dietary regimen continued	No relapse in any sign and symptom.
Follow-up 9	30/04/2023	Only dietary regimen continued	No recurrence found. No relapse in any sign and symptom.

Discussion

Psoriasis is an autoimmune disease where genetic and environmental factors have a significant role. Moreover, cytokines, inflammatory cascade, and keratinocytes play an important role in the

pathogenesis of psoriasis[3]. Among different types of psoriasis, palmoplantar psoriasis is the form of psoriasis where itching, pain and fissuring symptoms on palm and feet were observed. Being an autoimmune disease, it is quite difficult to treat. Therefore, one can opt for integrated treatment approach for its early management.

In present case, the patient was following the excess use of salty and sour food items, old butter and curd, spicy food, simultaneous use of milk products and salty snacks, etc. The patient was taking modern medications without sidestepping the causative factors as par *Ayurveda*. Therefore, temporary relief had observed with a relapsing pattern during the previous treatment. Thus, in the present case, the strict dietary regimen (*Pathya*) has been advised as the mitigating intervention along with integrated medicines.

The ongoing pathological changes were attenuated and corrected followed by integrated medications such as Injection 1. Kenacort 40mg Intramuscular, 2. *Panchtiktaghrith guggulu* (Tablet), 3. *Gandhaka rasayana* (Tablet), 4. *Mahatiktaka ghrita*, 5. *Mahamanjishthadi kwath*, 6. Urtiplex Lotion with Gammascab Lotion, 7. Immupsora oil, 8. Dr Reckeweg R65 Psoriasis Drops, 10. Strict dietary plan.

1. Kenacort 40mg IM- It contains triamcinolone as its active component a steroid medicine. It is used to relieve symptoms like itchy, red and sore patches on the skin. This medicine is also used in the treatment of psoriatic arthritis, an autoimmune disease, characterized by red patches of skin with silvery scales and swelling, stiffness, and pain in the joints.
2. *Panchtiktaghrith guggulu* (Tablet)- is an *Ayurvedic* supplement that can help enhance healthy skin. The tablet aids maintaining the healthy digestive functions of body. It can effectively improve the strength of bones and joints assuaging inflammation.[4]
3. *Gandhaka rasayana* (Tablet)- This formulation is most valuable in treating all types of infections owing to its potent antibiotic trait. It is mainly used to treat skin disorders, bleeding disorder, enhance skin complexion and immunity.[5]

4. *Mahatiktaka ghrita*- Is a medicated ghee used for *Shaman chikitsa*. *Ghee* has '*sukshmasrotogamitwa*' action hence can subside *doshas* from *Rasa, Rakta, Mamsa, Meda* and also nourishes the skin. Various active

phytoconstituents extracted in the *Mahatiktaka ghrita* work synergistically to cure psoriasis, possibly through the liposomal drug delivery system.[6]

5. *Mahamanjishthadi* (Herbal fermented liquid)- It purifies and improve the quality of blood as it possesses anti-bacterial, mild laxative and diuretic properties hence beneficial in treating all types of skin disorders like eczema, urticaria and psoriasis.[7]
6. Urtiplex lotion - It cools and soothes skin, support anti-allergic action, helps relieve itching, helps reduce flare-ups which helps to reduce burning and intense itching immediately.[8]
7. Gammascab lotion- It belongs to class of medications called anti parasitic drugs. it used to treat skin disease marked by itching and small raised red spots infestation with lice. In the present study Gammascab lotion has been applied with Urtiplex lotion to overcome the superadded infection. Scratching a rash, break the skin and lead to a superadded infection which is more serious and difficult to treat.[9]
8. Immupsora oil - It is a comprehensive topical formulation for psoriasis. *Neem* oil, *karanj* oil, *haridra* oil, *yashtimadhu* and *kumari* effectively help in the dry, itchy, scaly skin of psoriasis. It also exhibits antiseptic and anti-inflammatory properties.[10]
9. Dr. Reckeweg R65 psoriasis drops- Its homeopathy medication helps manage skin conditions such as psoriasis and dryness. This medicine is being used to avoid recurrence.[11]
10. Strict dietary plan- The intake of *Viruddha ahara* (the unwholesome dietary practices) is one of the important causative factors in the etiopathogenesis of skin diseases. The patient should avoid *Viruddha ahara* for better treatment

response, speedy recovery, and to avert the recurrence in chronic skin ailments as *Nidan-Parivarjan* said to be the first line of treatment.

The promising outcomes in the present case are a combined effect of all the *Ayurveda*, allopathy and homeopathic medicines, also *pathya sevana* (a strict

diet plan), and regular follow-ups by the patient. The possible mechanism and role of integrated medicines in the *Samprapti-vighatana* (counteracting the pathophysiology) of psoriasis have seen.

Patient perspective

The patient shared her perspective about the Integrated treatment in her local (Marathi) language. She had severe itching, burning sensation, and stress at the time of presentation, while she was free from all the signs and symptoms at the end of treatment and also recurrence has not seen till now even after two years of follow up.

Conclusion

In the present case, the treatment protocol was adopted as per *Ayurvedic* samprapti and modern pathophysiology the treatment response was observed much earlier as compared to previous treatment. No recurrence reported after the end of active treatment. The importance of a wholesome diet as a health promoter is also revalidated. The external and internal medications help to correct the complex pathophysiology of psoriasis like chronic diseases. Altogether, integrated treatment led to speedy and substantial recovery from a chronic case of psoriasis.

Informed consent

Consent of the patient was obtained for the photographs and before reporting the case report for publication.

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